

Resource Aware Adaptive Link Weight based Dynamic Routing and Spectrum Allocation in Elastic Optical Network

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Abstract—Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) are next-generation technology for growing traffic demands. Routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) algorithms run on the software-defined networking (SDN) controller and help in the efficient resource provisioning for the requested demands. The routing algorithm selects the shortest path between the source-destination nodes and the SA algorithm assigns the requested frequency slots (FSs) in the path links by satisfying spectrum constraints. The routing is of two types, static and dynamic. The static routing selects the fixed shortest path each time between the given source-destination nodes while the dynamic routing is flexible and selects the path depending upon the link status and resource availability between the source-destination node pair. The drawback of the static routing is the overburdening of the link resources because of the selection of the pre-defined fixed routes between source-destination nodes resulting in increased request-blocking probability (RBP). Therefore this paper has proposed a dynamic routing and spectrum allocation with an adaptive link weight (DRSA-ALW) algorithm that modifies the link weights with the arrived traffic and selects the path depending on the link resource availability. The simulation results demonstrate that the DRSA-ALW algorithm provides uniform traffic distribution resulting in efficient resource provisioning and reduced RBP as compared to the benchmark algorithm.

Index Terms—Elastic optical network, Dynamic Routing, Resource aware Adaptive Link Weight, Uniform traffic distribution.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growth in the use of Internet technology has led to increasing traffic demand. Elastic optical networks (EONs), an Optical-Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (O-OFDM) based transmission technology, handle this growing bandwidth requirement with flexible resource allocation. A bandwidth request can be allocated in an integer multiple of basic bandwidth slot size, i.e. 12.5 GHz as standardized

by ITU-T G.694.1 [1]. The software-defined networking (SDN) controller optimizes the resource provisioning in the network with the help of routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) algorithms. The routing algorithm fetches the least cost path between the source-destination node pair for the arrived connection request (CR) and the SA algorithm assigns the required frequency slots (FSs) in the path links by satisfying the spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints. The spectrum contiguity ensures that the allocated FSs in path links should be adjacent and spectrum continuity ensures that the indices of allocated FSs should be the same in path links. Various authors in [2]-[5] have discussed and solved problems related to Routing and Spectrum Allocation (RSA) in EONs. This paper explores the routing sub-problem of RSA. The routing is of two types, fixed or static routing and adaptive or dynamic Routing. The fixed routing uses the single pre-computed fixed path for each source-destination pair, whereas adaptive routing (AR) dynamically computes routes based on the current state information of the links [6]. The proposed dynamic routing and spectrum allocation with adaptive link weight (DRSA-ALW) is an adaptive routing-based algorithm.

Authors in the review paper [7] have discussed different static routing-based algorithms. Maurice Pollack [8] stated an algorithm to find the best ‘K’ routes between any source-destination pair, that finds the first shortest path with ‘m’ links using the shortest path routing algorithm and to get the second shortest path, the weight of all the ‘m’ links in the first route are set to ‘infinity’. This process is repeated until ‘K’ disjoint shortest paths are identified. However, this algorithm becomes computationally expensive if ‘K’ is large. Walter Hoffman *et al.* [9] finds the shortest path from source node ‘i’ to all other nodes in the network, which form the shortest path spanning tree. This algorithm is based on

the Routing in which loops are allowed. Papers [10]-[11] are based on the adaptive routing. Author Anjali Sharma *et al.* in [10] have proposed penalty-based adaptive routing. The algorithm searches the shortest path for the arrived CR, and if the spectrum constraints are not satisfied in path links, the CR gets blocked, and the weights of path links are increased. The increment in the link weight is proportional to the deficit in the resources on the link. The link weight decreases when the CR expires, and the reduction in the link weights depends on a fraction proportional to the ratio of contiguously available FSs to total available FSs in the links.

Any adaptive weight-based routing method should ensure that the mean weight value is always stable and should not constantly increase or decrease. With this objective, this paper proposes an algorithm where the link weights in the network increase dynamically with each CR getting established and decreases when the CR is released.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II defines the proposed algorithm. In Section III, the numerical results are shown in which performance metrics, simulation results, and performance improvement have been discussed. The paper is concluded in Section IV.

II. DYNAMIC ROUTING AND SPECTRUM ALLOCATION WITH ADAPTIVE LINK WEIGHT (DRSA-ALW)

A. Idea behind the proposed algorithm

The DRSA-ALW proposes dynamic routing with adaptive updation of the link weights. The algorithm that runs on the SDN controller keeps track of the link resource utilization and aims to distribute the arrived CRs uniformly in the network. The DRSA-ALW uses two key pieces of information of the network to achieve the desired uniform traffic distribution, the first is that the links' resources are utilized with established CRs and get free with expiring CRs, and the second is the SDN controller fetches the shortest path for each arrived CR, the DRSA-ALW combines these two network operation. The DRSA-ALW algorithm increases the weight W of path links whenever the resources get utilized and due to the increased W the same path does not remain the shortest path hence the algorithm will fetch the other shortest path for the next arrived CR. When CRs expire, the link resources get free and the algorithm reduces the weight of path links so that these can be fetched as the shortest path for the next arrived traffic. The DRSA-ALW proposes two algorithms, dynamic routing and spectrum allocation with unity adaptive link weight (DRSA-UALW) and dynamic routing and spectrum allocation with frequency slots adaptive link weight (DRSA-FSALW). The DRSA-UALW uses the number of times the links' resources get utilized to update the link weight i.e. the path links' weight gets updated with each established CR and the DRSA-FSALW updates the path links' weight based on the allocated FSs to them.

(a) Path set-up for $CR(B, E, 37.5Gbps)$

(b) **DRSA-UALW** increases the path links' weight $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow F \rightarrow E$ by 1, resulting in selection of $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow G \rightarrow E$ path for next arrived $CR(B, E)$

(c) **DRSA-FSALW** increases the path links' weight $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow F \rightarrow E$ by 3, resulting in selection of $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow G \rightarrow E$ path for next arrived $CR(B, E)$

Figure 1

B. Proposed Algorithms

Algorithm 1 describes the flow chart for the DRSA-ALW algorithm. When a connection request $CR(s, d, SS_r)$ arrives with a demand of b Gbps in a network $G(V, E, SS, W)$ having V sets of vertices and E sets of edges with weights W and a capacity of SS FSs (lines 1 and 2). The algorithm fetches the shortest path with i number of path links by $K=1$ shortest path routing algorithm using W of $G(V, E, SS, W)$ and calculates the requested FSs SS_r using Eq. 1 (lines

3,4, and 5). The algorithm checks spectrum continuity and contiguity in path links. If both spectrum constraints are not satisfied, the CR gets blocked (lines 6,7,8, and 9), but if both are satisfied the CR gets established (lines 10 and 11), and path links' resources get utilized, to avoid overburdening in path links and ensure uniform traffic distribution, the W^i of i path links get increased. Since the paper proposes two separate algorithms, the weight is increased as $W^i = W + 1$ for **DRSA-UALW** (line 12) and $W^i = W + SS_r$ for **DRSA-FSALW** (line 13). Updated link weights modify the weight matrix W^i and the modified $G(V, E, SS, W^i)$ will be used to find the shortest path for the next CR (lines 14, and 15).

When CR holding time is over, the algorithm releases all the FSs occupied in i path links resulting in available resources (lines 16, and 17), and the link weights are decreased as $W = W^i - 1$ for **DRSA-UALW** (line 18) and $W = W^i - SS_r$ for **DRSA-FSALW** (line 19). The algorithm uses the Updated $G(V, E, SS, W)$ for the next CR (lines 20, and 21).

$$SS_r = \frac{b}{12.5} \quad (1)$$

Let us consider a $CR(B, E, 37.5)$ arrives in the network Figure.1(a) between the source node B and the destination node E , with a data demand b of $37.5Gbps$. The algorithm fetches the shortest path $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow F \rightarrow E$ using the shortest path algorithm and computes SS_r from Eq.1 i.e. 3. The availability of SS_r is checked in path links with the spectrum constraints. If constraints are satisfied, the SA is done and the weight is increased with unity for **DRSA-UALW** Figure. 1(b) and with SS_r for **DRSA-FSALW** Figure. 1(c). Due to the updated link weight, if the next CR arrives between the same $B-E$ pairs, the routing algorithm fetches the new shortest path, i.e. $B \rightarrow A \rightarrow G \rightarrow E$ as shown in Figure. 1(b) and 1(c).

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Network Settings

The simulation is done on a USNET topology with 24 nodes and 43 bidirectional links (Figure.2). The C-band of the optical spectrum with a usable bandwidth of 4 THz is used for optical communication and the FS granularity of 12.5 GHz provides a link capacity of 320 FSs. The traffic is generated according to the Poisson distribution with an arrival rate (λ). The holding time is exponentially distributed with the average service time ($\frac{1}{\mu}$). The average traffic load at each node $\frac{\lambda}{\mu}$ varies between 5 to 50 erlangs. The bandwidth requirement is randomly distributed between 25 to 200Gbps. The simulation is done for 10 iterations each with 200000 CRs. The simulation results are plotted with a 95% confidence interval. The time complexity of the K=1 RSA and DRSA-ALW using a single shortest path is $O(V^2 + E.SS)$ and $O(V^2 + 2.E.SS)$ respectively [10].

Algorithm 1 DRSA-ALW: Dynamic Routing and Spectrum Allocation with Adaptive Link weight

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1: Input: Network graph  $G(V, E, SS, W)$  and  $CR(s, d, b)$ 
2: if event == arrival then
3:   Fetch the shortest path between  $s, d$  using a weight matrix  $W$  of  $G(V, E, SS, W)$ .
4:   The path contains  $i$  number of links.
5:   Calculate  $SS_r$  using Eq. 1.
6:   Check whether the spectrum constraints are satisfied in  $i$  links.
7:   if not then
8:     Block the Connection.
9:     return
10:  else
11:    Set up the connection.
    // For the DRSA-UALW algorithm
12:    Update weight  $W^i = W + 1$  of  $i$  path links. // For the DRSA-FSALW algorithm
13:    Update weight  $W^i = W + SS_r$  of  $i$  path links.
14:    return Updated  $G(V, E, SS, W^i)$  to compute shortest path for the next CR.
15:  end if
16: else if event==release then
17:   Free the FSs occupied by the expired CRs.
    // For the DRSA-UALW algorithm
18:   Update weight  $W^i = W - 1$  of  $i$  path links. // For the DRSA-FSALW algorithm
19:   Update weight  $W^i = W - SS_r$  of  $i$  path links.
20:   return Updated  $G(V, E, SS, W)$  to compute shortest path for the next CR.
21: end if

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The K=1 RSA is utilized as the benchmark algorithm due to its nature as a static routing-based approach, in contrast to the proposed adaptive routing-based algorithm. This allows for a comparative analysis of both routing methodologies within this paper. Additionally, the K=1 RSA provides non-uniform traffic distribution because of using consistent pre-defined route. In contrast, the DRSA-ALW algorithm facilitates a uniform traffic distribution across the network. This comparison enables an examination of how network performance is influenced by both non-uniform and uniform traffic distributions.

B. Performance Metrics

The Performance Metrics provide a quantitative measure of the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm with respect to the benchmark algorithm.

1) *Request Blocking Probability (RBP)*: RBP represents the ratio of total blocked CRs to total requested CRs, as indicated in Equation 2. The simulation results for RBP, comparing the benchmark and proposed algorithms, are illustrated in Figure 3 which shows that the DRSA-ALW

Figure 2: USNET topology

algorithms consistently demonstrate a lower RBP across all loads compared to the K=1 RSA. This improvement is attributed to the proposed algorithms' ability to uniformly distribute incoming traffic throughout the network by dynamically adjusting the weights of path links. These weights inform the SDN controller about the utilization levels of the path links, guiding the selection process for future path computations of newly arrived CRs. In contrast, the K=1 RSA employs a fixed route for each source-destination pair, failing to provide the SDN controller with insights into the network's state. This oversight results in the overloading of frequently used links, consequently leading to an increase in RBP shown by Table I, which represents the percentage reduction in RBP for the DRSA-ALW algorithms relative to the K=1 RSA algorithm.

$$\text{RBP} = \frac{\text{Total blocked CRs}}{\text{Total requested CRs}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: RBP for USNET

2) *Bandwidth Blocking Probability (BBP)*: BBP represents the ratio of the total bandwidth that is blocked to the total bandwidth that is requested (refer to Equation 3). The simulation results for the K=1 RSA and DRSA-ALW algorithms are illustrated in Figure 4, demonstrating that the proposed algorithms consistently yield a lower

Traffic Load (in Erlangs)	% decrease in RBP for DRSA-UALW	% decrease in RBP for DRSA-FSALW	% decrease in BBP for DRSA-UALW	% decrease in BBP for DRSA-FSALW
5	-100 %	-100 %	-100 %	-100 %
10	-94.5 %	-95.1 %	-94.2 %	-94.8 %
15	-58.1 %	-58.7 %	-55.7 %	-56.2 %
20	-35.6 %	-35.2 %	-32.4 %	-32.0 %
25	-24.6 %	-24.2 %	-21.1 %	-20.8 %
30	-17.3 %	-16.9 %	-14.0 %	-13.5 %
35	-13.4 %	-13.3 %	-14.0 %	-13.5 %
40	-10.9 %	-11.0 %	-14.0 %	-13.5 %
45	-9.60 %	-9.51 %	-14.0 %	-13.5 %
50	-7.98 %	-7.71 %	-14.0 %	-13.5 %

Table I: Percentage decrease in RBP and BBP with respect to the benchmark algorithm

BBP. As previously mentioned in the context of network configurations, the requested bandwidths exhibit heterogeneity; some requests are for larger bandwidths while others are for smaller ones. Consequently, larger bandwidth requests must adhere to spectrum contiguity and continuity constraints in order to be established. However, for the K=1 RSA, satisfying these spectrum contiguity constraints on frequently used links proves challenging due to the presence of numerous non-contiguous available spectrum slices (link fragments). In contrast, an analysis of the DRSA-ALW algorithm reveals that its adaptive routing capabilities allow for the utilization of links with greater available resources that have not been optimally used (less congested links). This facilitates the accommodation of larger bandwidth requests, resulting in a reduction in BBP, as illustrated in Table I, which presents the percentage decrease in BBP for the DRSA-ALW algorithms compared to the K=1 RSA.

$$\text{BBP} = \frac{\text{Total bandwidth blocked}}{\text{Total bandwidth requested}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4: BBP for USNET

3) *Accepted Load (AL) and Fractional Spectrum Utilization (FSU)*: The AL represents the quantity of traffic load that is accepted (refer to Equation 4). The FSU indicates the average ratio of total occupied FSs to the total FSs

across all links. Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the simulation results of both the benchmark and proposed algorithms concerning the AL and FSU. As previously mentioned, the proposed resource-aware algorithm enhances resource utilization through adaptive routing, which is facilitated by the dynamic updation of link weights. This process aids the SDN controller in making resource management decisions, resulting in the establishment of more connections and an increase in the accepted load. This, in turn, leads to a greater number of occupied FSs, as indicated by Equation 5. A higher number of occupied FSs correlates with an increased FSU, as detailed in Table II.

$$\text{Accepted Load} = \text{Traffic Load} * (1 - \text{RBP}) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{FSU} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^E (\text{Occupied Spectrum Slots})_i}{\sum_{i=1}^E (\text{Total Spectrum Slots})_i} \quad (5)$$

Figure 5: Accepted Load for USNET

Figure 6: FSU for USNET

Traffic Load (in Erlangs)	% increase in AL for DRSA-UALW	% change in FSU for DRSA-UALW	% increase in AL for DRSA-FSALW	% change in FSU for DRSA-FSALW
5	0.018 %	-1.40 %	0.018 %	-0.88%
10	3.77 %	5.61%	3.79 %	6.09 %
15	7.10 %	11.7%	7.17 %	12.0 %
20	7.50 %	12.1%	7.42 %	11.8 %
25	7.24 %	11.0%	7.12 %	11.1 %
30	6.39 %	10.0%	6.22 %	9.97 %
35	5.89 %	9.10 %	5.85 %	8.97 %
40	5.60 %	7.85 %	5.66 %	8.03 %
45	5.59 %	6.96 %	5.54 %	7.28 %
50	5.17 %	6.26 %	5.00 %	6.58 %

Table II: Percentage change in AL and FSU with respect to the benchmark algorithm

4) *Entropy-based Fragmentation Metric (EBFM)*: The EBFM evaluates the link fragments (n_l) and their respective sizes ($f_{i,l}$) as indicated in Equation 6. The EBFM plot illustrating the simulation results of both the benchmark and proposed algorithms is presented in Figure 7. Table III details the percentage increase in the EBFM for DRSA-ALW in comparison to the K=1 RSA. To comprehend this, it is essential to note that a greater establishment of CRs results in an increased number of link fragments. This phenomenon occurs because the heterogeneous bandwidth generates more non-contiguous free spectrum slices within the link, attributed to its dynamic arrival and departure. As depicted in Figures 3, 4 and 5, the DRSA-ALW approach yields a lower RBP, BBP and a higher accepted load, which contributes to an enhanced EBFM. Conversely, the K=1 RSA exhibits a higher RBP and a lower accepted load, leading to fewer link fragments and a diminished EBFM.

$$\text{EBFM} = \frac{1}{E} \sum_{l=1}^E \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} \frac{f_{i,l}}{SS_l} * \ln \frac{SS_l}{f_{i,l}} \quad (6)$$

Figure 7: EBFM for USNET

Traffic Load (in Erlangs)	% increase in EBFM for DRSA-UALW	% increase in EBFM for DRSA-FSALW	% change in EFM for DRSA-UALW	% change in EFM for DRSA-FSALW
5	1.30 %	1.61 %	-8.84 %	-8.88 %
10	12.2 %	12.4 %	8.21 %	8.51 %
15	13.0 %	13.2 %	13.5 %	13.7 %
20	10.8 %	10.7 %	12.4 %	12.3 %
25	8.75 %	8.60 %	10.8 %	10.9 %
30	6.91 %	6.95 %	9.36 %	9.27 %
35	5.75 %	5.60 %	8.05 %	7.90 %
40	4.78 %	4.59 %	6.87 %	6.76 %
45	4.14 %	3.95 %	6.04 %	5.98 %
50	3.20 %	3.05 %	5.04 %	5.10 %

Table III: Percentage increase in EBFM and EFM with respect to the benchmark algorithm

5) *External Fragmentation Metric (EFM)*: The EFM represents the ratio of the largest contiguous spectrum slots available to the total number of unoccupied FSs across all links, as defined by Equation 7. This equation indicates that an EFM value of 0 signifies that all free FSs in the links are contiguous (there could be possibility that all the FSs of the links are available), while a value of 1 indicates that all FSs are occupied. Additionally, Table III illustrates the percentage change in EFM for the DRSA-ALW algorithm in comparison to the K=1 RSA. By integrating these two discussions, it can be concluded that the proposed algorithm achieves a higher EFM (as shown in Figure 8) than the benchmark algorithm. This implies that the proposed algorithm utilizes more FSs and provides increased AL, leading to reduced RBP, BBP and increased FSU, same conclusions can be drawn from Figures 3, 4, 5 and 6.

$$EFM = \frac{1}{E} \sum_{i=1}^E 1 - \frac{\text{Largest Free Contiguous FSs}_i}{\text{Total Free FSs}_i} \quad (7)$$

Figure 8: EFM for USNET

At a load of 5 erlangs, the FSU and EFM for the DRSA-ALW is lower, as the FSU and EFM is contingent upon the occupied FSs, which are influenced by holding time. It is possible that a dynamic holding time may yield a lower FSU and less link fragments for the proposed algorithm.

However, when compared to the RBP and BBP at traffic load of 5 erlangs, the DRSA-ALW algorithm demonstrates a lower RBP and BBP while consuming fewer resources, which is advantageous for the proposed approach.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has proposed a DRSA-ALW algorithm that updates the path link weight with each established and released CR. The simulation results demonstrate that the DRSA-ALW algorithm is more efficient at lower loads and provides a significant amount of reduction in RBP and efficient resource provisioning as compared to the K=1 RSA.

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